

Influence of Crystallite Size on the Structure, Optical and Electrical Properties of Pure and Ni doped SnO₂ Nanoparticles

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Abstract:

Pure and Ni doped SnO₂ nanoparticles were prepared by Microwave assisted co-precipitated method. The prepared pure and Ni doped SnO₂ nanoparticles were characterized by X-Ray diffraction (XRD), Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy (FTIR), UV – Visible absorption Spectroscopy and AC impedance spectroscopy studies. The XRD pattern reveals the tetragonal rutile structure of SnO₂. The FTIR studies confirmed the vibrational modes of Sn and Oxygen were presented in pure and SnO₂ nanoparticles. The band gap is increased with doping concentration of Ni in SnO₂. The electrical properties of the synthesised nanoparticles were analysed from AC impedance analysis. The pure tin oxide gives high conductivity when compared to Ni doped SnO₂ nanoparticles. Hence, the SnO₂ quantum dots would be promising material for gas sensor, solar cell and optoelectronic device applications.

Key Words: Co – Precipitation method, Nanoparticles, AC Impedance Spectroscopy, Band gap

Introduction:

Nanotechnology is a developing technology for last two decades in worldwide. Nanomaterials create the digital era due to their peculiar properties. The shape, size and quantum effects of nanomaterials enhance their unique electrical, optical, chemical and magnetic properties [1, 2]. Particularly, Semiconductor nanostructured materials are used in gas sensor applications due to their

oxygen vacancy [3,4,5]. Tin oxide is a wide band gap semiconductor broadly used for potential applications such as catalyst for hydrocarbon oxidation, transport conducting oxides, gas sensors and optoelectronic devices [6-8].

Among other metal oxide nanostructures such as TiO_2 and ZnO , tin oxide gave the better magnetic performance in the existence of magnetic and non-magnetic dopant ions [9]. Several studies on transition metal (TM) doped semiconducting oxides have room temperature magnetic applications [10, 11]. The dopant material and annealing temperature also tuned the properties of nanostructured SnO_2 [12-14]. The transition metal (TM) doping of SnO_2 have the pragmatic properties used to create the electrical storage devices. [15]. The dopants materials play the significant role to tune the surface area, grain size and crystallinity [16, 17]. Various methods have been used to prepare the nanoparticles at different grain size by electrochemical deposition, magnetron sputtering, pulse laser deposition, sol-gel, hydrothermal, spray pyrolysis and microwave assisted co-precipitation method [18-20]. In the present research work, Ni doped tin oxide nanoparticles were prepared by microwave assisted co-precipitation method. Pure SnO_2 and Ni doped SnO_2 nanoparticles were characterized by X – ray diffraction, Fourier Transform Infrared spectroscopy (FTIR), UV – Vis spectroscopy and conductivity studies.

Experimental details:

Pure SnO_2 and Ni doped SnO_2 nanoparticles have prepared from high purity $SnCl_2 \cdot 2H_2O$ (Sigma aldrich, India), $NiCl_2 \cdot 2H_2O$, ammonia (Hayman) and double distilled water by microwave assisted co-precipitation method. The chemicals were used without further purification. The 0.1 M of tin chloride dehydrate ($SnCl_2 \cdot 2H_2O$) is dissolved in 100 ml of aqueous water. The solution is stirred and ammonia solution is slowly added to the solution. The solution is kept in microwave oven to produce the

precipitation. Finally, the precipitate was centrifuged and cleaned using the distilled water. The precipitate was dried by microwave oven. The same above process followed to prepare Ni doped SnO₂ nanoparticles. Samples namely D1, D2, D3, D4 and D5 have synthesised using the ratio of Sn_{0.19}Ni_{0.01}O₂, Sn_{0.18}Ni_{0.02}O₂, Sn_{0.17}Ni_{0.03}O₂, Sn_{0.16}Ni_{0.04}O₂, and Sn_{0.15}Ni_{0.05}O₂ respectively.

Characterizations:

Structural characterization was done by STOE powder X-ray diffractometer with CuK_α radiation ($\lambda = 0.15406$ nm) in the 2θ range from 20 to 80°. By knowing the full-width at half-maximum ($\beta_{1/2}$) and the angle of diffraction (θ) of the XRD peaks, the average particle size (D_{XRD}) of samples was obtained using Scherrer's equation [21]. UV visible studies were carried out in a Perkin Elmer UV-vis spectrometer (Lambda 650) in the range from 200 to 800 nm with 1 nm resolution. The FTIR studies were carried out by Shimadzu FTIR spectrophotometer with amplitude waves ranging from 400 to 4000 cm⁻¹. The functional group of synthesized nanoparticles were revealed from recorded FTIR pattern. Electrical conductivity was obtained using HIOKI 3351 – 01 LCR Hi tester (France) in the range between 50 Hz to 1 MHz at various temperatures.

Results and discussions:

XRD Analysis:

Fig. 1 shows the XRD pattern of pure SnO₂ and Ni doped SnO₂ nanoparticles. The observed XRD pattern have confirmed the rutile structure and it was compared with JCPDS data (card No:41-1445). The pure SnO₂ and Ni doped SnO₂ nanoparticles exhibit three major axes appears at 27.3°, 33.8°, 51.5° respectively. The peaks come out at (101) phase ($2\theta \approx 27.3$), (1 1 0) phase ($2\theta \approx 33.8$), (2 1 1) phase

($2\theta \approx 51.5$). The structural properties and average size of synthesised nanoparticles have tabulated in Table. 1 and 2.

Fig. 1. XRD pattern of pure and Ni doped SnO₂ nanoparticles

Table 1 : Structural parameters of synthesised nanoparticles

SAMPLE	(h k l) planes	d-spacing(A)	parameters
JCPDS(41-1445)	(101)	3.3470	a=4.7382 c=3.1871
	(110)	2.2627	
	(211)	1.7641	

Table 2 : Average crystallite size of pure SnO₂ and Ni doped SnO₂ nanoparticles

Sample Name	2θ (degree)	θ (radian)	FWHM(θ) (degree)	B (radian)	D (nm)
Pure	26.40052	0.23048	1.43567	0.02507	7.38067×10 ⁻⁹
D1	26.41983	0.23065	1.29503	0.02261	6.58423×10 ⁻⁹
D2	26.27307	0.23284	0.05071	0.08541	5.93790×10 ⁻⁹
D3	26.19671	0.22870	0.0321	0.05605	4.26961×10 ⁻⁹
D4	26.49029	0.23126	1.1548	0.02016	2.65481×10 ⁻⁹
D5	26.17307	0.22849	0.01996	0.03485	1.74389×10 ⁻⁹

From the Fig.1, it is clearly seen that, the doping of Ni to the pure SnO₂ does not change the tetragonal structure of SnO₂. Hence the doping concentration does not change the structure [22]. Table.2 indicates, the intensity of the peaks decreases when increases the concentration of Ni. There is a strong connection accumulated between the intensity and doping concentration [23]. The crystalline size of synthesised nanoparticles has been obtained by using Scherrer's formula. They have been 7.38, 6.58, 5.93, 4.26, 2.65 and 1.74 nm for pure SnO₂, Ni doped SnO₂ with various concentration as D1, D2, D3, D4 and D5 respectively. It is evidently seen that; the particle size of the Ni doped Tin oxide nanoparticles decreases when the Ni concentration is increased [24].

FTIR Studies

The FTIR spectrum of pure SnO₂ and Ni doped SnO₂ has shown in Fig.2. The four main characteristic peaks are exhibited by the FTIR spectrum of pure SnO₂ and Ni doped SnO₂. The peak shows around 540 – 620 cm⁻¹, which refers the Sn – O stretching modes of Sn-O-Sn [25]. The peak

appears around $1600-1680\text{ cm}^{-1}$, $2260-2500\text{ cm}^{-1}$ and $3150-3450\text{ cm}^{-1}$, which refers the stretching vibration of water molecules [26].

Fig 2. FTIR spectrum of pure SnO_2 and Ni doped SnO_2 nanoparticles

OPTICAL ANALYSIS

UV – VISIBLE ABSORPTION SPECTROSCOPY

The absorption spectrum of synthesized pure SnO_2 and Ni doped SnO_2 nanoparticles recorded in the UV – vis region is shown in Fig. 3. It exposes that the absorption in the near ultraviolet region (200 – 400 nm) occurs from the electronic transitions associated with high energy charge transfer between Ni^{4+} and Sn^{2+} interaction of the prepared nanoparticles[27]. The absorbance depends upon the band gap, surface roughness and impurity centres [28]. The optical band gap energy is calculated by the Tauc plot. Tau plot for pure and Ni doped SnO_2 quantum dots are represented in Fig.4. The corresponding band

gap values are tabulated in Table.4. From the table, the band gap values are 2.09, 2.45, 2.50, 2.68, 2.80 and 2.88 eV correspond to D1, D2, D3, D4, D5 and Pure SnO₂ specimens respectively. It is clearly seen that, pure SnO₂ sample has large band gap energy rather than Ni doped SnO₂ specimens. It is also evidently proved that, in Ni doped SnO₂ nanoparticles, there is an increasing of doping concentration of Ni, the band gap value has been increased.

Figure 3. UV-Vis absorption spectra of pure SnO₂ and Ni doped SnO₂ nanoparticles.

Figure 4. Tauc plot for pure SnO₂ and Ni doped SnO₂ nanoparticles

Table 4: Band gap of synthesized nanoparticles

Sample	Bandgap (eV)
Pure	3.01
D1	2.79
D2	3.5
D3	3.11
D4	3.09
D5	3.12

ELECTRICAL ANALYSIS

AC IMPEDANCE SPECTROSCOPY

The a.c impedance technique has been a prevailing device for characterizing the electrical properties of materials. Conductance spectra of pure SnO₂ and Ni doped SnO₂ nanoparticles at room temperature have shown in the Fig.5. The conductivity of the prepared nanoparticles was found from the figure. The conductivity has been calculated from the impedance plot and has been tabulated in Table 5.

Fig. 5: Conductance spectra of pure SnO₂ and Ni doped SnO₂ nanoparticles at room temperature.

Table 5 : Conductance spectra of pure and Ni doped SnO₂ nano particles.

COMPOSITIONS	CONDUCTIVITY(S/cm)
D5	7.461×10 ⁻⁷
D4	1.698×10 ⁻⁶
D3	1.192×10 ⁻⁶
D2	1.125×10 ⁻⁶
D1	1.537×10 ⁻⁶
Pure	6.553×10 ⁻⁶

The maximum value of conductivity is observed as 6.553×10⁻⁶ s/cm for pure tin oxide nanoparticles. When Ni is added to the pure SnO₂ nanoparticles the conductivity is decreased rather than pure tin oxide nanoparticles. The conductivity of all Ni doped SnO₂ nanoparticles are 1.537×10⁻⁶, 1.125×10⁻⁶, 1.192×10⁻⁶, 1.698×10⁻⁶ and 7.461×10⁻⁷, (S/cm) for D1, D2, D3, D4 and D5 respectively. It is clearly seen that when adding a doping concentration of Ni, the conductivity of SnO₂ nanoparticles has been decreased. It indicates that the prepared pure SnO₂ nanoparticles have been in conductor nature [29].

The cole–cole plot for pure SnO₂ and Ni doped SnO₂ nanoparticles have shown in the Fig.6. The ion conductivity of all synthesised nanoparticles has calculated from cole-cole plot. The calculated values are tabulated in Table.6. The highest value of ionic conductivity is observed as 9.221×10⁻⁶ s/cm

for pure tin oxide nanoparticles. From the table 6, it is evidently seen that, the ionic conductivity of nickel doped SnO₂ nanoparticles has been decreased rather than pure SnO₂ nanoparticles. Hence the ionic contribution of nickel, leads to decrease of ionic conductivity in the prepared nanoparticles [29].

Fig. 6. Cole–Cole plot for pure SnO₂ and Ni doped SnO₂ nanoparticles

Table 6. Cole - Cole plot data of pure SnO₂ and Ni doped SnO₂ nano particles

COMPOSITIONS	CONDUCTIVITY(S/cm)
D5	5.189×10^{-7}
D4	7.011×10^{-6}
D3	1.564×10^{-6}
D2	9.243×10^{-6}
D1	4.467×10^{-6}
Pure	9.221×10^{-6}

Conclusion:

Pure SnO₂ and Ni doped SnO₂ nanoparticles with tetragonal rutile structure were successfully prepared by a microwave assisted co-precipitation method. From XRD analysis, it is clearly

seen that, the doping of Ni to the pure SnO₂ does not change the tetragonal structure of SnO₂. Further, it is evidently seen that, the particle size of the Ni doped Tin oxide nanoparticles decreases when the Ni concentration is increased. The functional groups that present in the prepared nanoparticles have found in the FTIR spectrum. UV – Vis spectroscopy study reveals that, the absorption in the near ultraviolet region occurs from the electronic transitions associated with high energy charge transfer between Ni⁴⁺ and Sn²⁺ interaction of the prepared nanoparticles. In addition, there is a large optical band gap energy has observed for pure SnO₂ nanoparticle rather than Ni doped SnO₂ nanoparticles. From the AC impedance analysis, it is observed that, when Ni is added to the pure SnO₂ nanoparticles the conductivity is decreased rather than pure tin oxide nanoparticles. It indicates that the prepared pure SnO₂ nanoparticles have been in conductor nature. The pure tin oxide gives high conductivity when compared to Ni doped SnO₂ nanoparticles. Hence, the SnO₂ quantum dots would be promising material for gas sensor, solar cell and optoelectronic device applications.

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Conflict of interest

There is no conflict of interest

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